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Examination of the Problems that Teachers Face During Vocational Education

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Abstract

The purpose of this research is to determine the problems faced by the teachers who give vocational courses during their vocational practice. A semi-structured interview form was used in order to collect the data required for the research. The research is a qualitative study and it was carried out in order to determine the opinions of teachers about the problems encountered in vocational education. The case study method, which is one of the qualitative research methods, was used in the research. All the data obtained in the research were analyzed by coding with the content analysis method. The study group of the research consists of a total of 30 vocational course teachers, 21 male and 9 female, working in state vocational high schools in the central districts of Hatay province in the 2020-2021 academic year, and they participated in the research on a voluntary basis. In the research, one conclusion was that the students who receive vocational education have sufficient skills for business life, albeit partially, that students sometimes have difficulties in adapting to the work discipline, and that there may be problems due to cognitive, affective and psychomotor, that is, individual characteristics, especially during internship training. In addition, in the research, it can be concluded that practical training should be carried out with a wider scope, physical facilities should be improved by giving more importance to vocational high schools, and students should be admitted to vocational education institutions with aptitude tests.

Keywords: Vocational Education, Technical Education, Vocational Practice, Training Course

1. Introduction

For people to continue their lives happily and efficiently depends primarily on having a job and being successful in their profession. Being successful in a profession depends on the theoretical and practical training to be taken related to the profession. The success of a student who is studying depends on the quality, qualification and characteristics of the school, the education s/he received when s/he finished school, and the efficiency and effectiveness of vocational practices (Desimone, 2011; Macia, & Garcia, 2016; Kang, et al. 2013). The individual's success in vocational education primarily depends on his/her self-belief, self-confidence or self-efficacy (Bozak, 2021). Self-efficacy is based on the idea that people's belief in themselves about how successful they can be have an impact on their performance and motivation (Bandura, 1982). The subject of success and self-efficacy in education is a concept that has been started to be researched in recent years and was used for the first time by Albert Bandura (Bandura, 1987). Perceived self-efficacy is related to the individual's beliefs in her/his ability to influence events that affect her/his life. This fundamental belief is the basis of human motivation, performance

achievements and emotional well-being (Bandura, 2010). In that case, it is necessary that the interns who will start vocational practice have high self-efficacy, self-confidence and self-belief.

In their senior year, especially in vocational schools, students go to vocational practices or internships in order to develop or increase their self-confidence and self-esteem (Donger et al., 2016; Sarigoz, 2016). The reason for these internships or vocational practices is to try to improve the vocational knowledge and skills of the interns in order to manage the process by the help of the teachers who take more active roles (Day, 2007; Fullan, 2001).

In the dictionary of the Turkish Language Institution (2017), internship or vocational practice is defined as the applied learning period spent by someone who will have a profession, and the period spent by a person working in one or more departments of an institution to increase her/his vocational knowledge. METARGEM, (1997) has defined vocational education as the educational process that enables the individual to acquire a profession in line with his/her interest, talent and ability in a field he/she wants and it aims to improve his/her abilities.

While vocational education enables people to lead their lives in prosperity, they also aim to increase the quality of life in the society by increasing the qualified workforce needed by the sector (Demir & Sen, 2009). For this reason, vocational education programs should be kept up-to-date, workshops should be equipped with advanced equipment, students should be placed in professions according to their interests, abilities and wishes and they should be prepared for life (Bozak, 2019). This situation will contribute to the countries to catch up with the era and become a civilized society in every sense, especially with qualified and well-educated individuals.

In today's schools, it is tried to combine cognitive, affective and psychomotor behaviors with the knowledge, critical thinking skills, practice, experience and achievements required by a profession through vocational education and practice teachers (Donnelly, 2008; Kutlu & Schreglmann, 2011). It is also among the aims of vocational education to disseminate the skills and experiences gained through laboratory and workplace practices throughout the education period of students studying in vocational and technical education regions, especially in vocational schools, to enable them to recognize their responsibilities, relationships, organization and production process, and to learn new technologies in the workplace (Official Gazette of the Republic of Turkey, 2002). In particular, subjects such as the vocational practices or internships of teacher candidates during their undergraduate education process are seen as the first step of business life, contributing to the theory-practice relationship, affecting vocational knowledge and skills, experiencing business life and giving an idea about the vocational future are also among the most important benefits of vocational education (Katajavuori et al., 2006).

With the Law No. 3308 on vocational education in Turkey, a change was made in 1988 regarding internships in workplaces and it has been seen that this law comprehensively regulates internship practices in schools, workplaces and companies (Kepenekci, 2008). Based on this law, the regulation regarding the internship of students at the workplace, which was made in 2002, was put into effect in vocational schools by the Ministry of National Education (Kuzgun, 2013). With this amendment, it is stated in the 5th article of the regulation that it is aimed for students to develop their vocational knowledge and skills, and to make a career in production and in the workplace (Regulation, 2007).

According to the reports of OECD (1995), vocational education has also been mentioned as a solution proposal for youth unemployment among the active employment measures for the young population. Vocational education gives students both work experience and job opportunities when they graduate (Gokdogan & Sarigoz, 2012; Sarigoz, 2016). Students not only gain experience from the vocational practice training they receive, but also teachers, educators and trainers who participate in internships increase their knowledge and experience thanks to their vocational practices. Counselors participating in vocational practice gain new information during practice, and gain insight into various new topics by reasoning and observation (Bozak, 2021). They also gain experience by observing problems from different perspectives. When interns encounter problems during their vocational practice, they gain experience and become more productive by solving these problems (Gokdogan & Sarigoz, 2012).

In addition, when interns who participate in vocational practice do not feel obliged to this practice and do it voluntarily, they can be more productive both for their workplaces and for themselves. If students do not see this course as an obligation and study it efficiently, it can also increase their personal success (Dogan et al., 2021). When a wide-ranging literature research was conducted on vocational practices, it was seen that there were some studies on vocational practices in high schools, vocational colleges and faculties, but there were not enough studies on vocational practices in high schools, vocational schools and faculties. Therefore, it was decided to conduct this research in order to give an idea to academicians, teachers, students and all educators.

1.1 Research Aim

The purpose of this research was to identify the problems faced by the teachers who give applied vocational courses in vocational high schools during this vocational education and to offer solutions to these problems. In addition, the importance of applied education in the research and its effects on the development of the country are the other the purposes of the research.

1.2 Problem of the Research

What are the problems faced by teachers who give applied courses or internship courses in vocational high schools during vocational education?

Sub-problems of the research

1. What are the opinions of the vocational course teachers about the lack of vocational competence of the students?
2. What are the opinions of the vocational course teachers about the working discipline and adaptability of the students who receive internship training in their workplaces?
3. What are the opinions of the vocational course teachers about the problems related to vocational practice training and the causes of the problems?
4. What are the opinions of the vocational course teachers about the achievement of the determined goal of the vocational practice training?
5. What are the opinions of vocational course teachers on the improvement of vocational education?

2. Method

This section consists of the model used in the research, the participants, the data collection tools of the research, how to obtain the data, the interview process, the findings obtained from the data and the analysis of the findings.

2.1 Research Model

The research is a qualitative study and it was carried out in order to determine the problems faced by vocational high school students who receive vocational education according to the opinions of teachers. In the research, by using the interview method, the answers given by the teachers to the questions were gathered and the case study method was used in the research because "the situations were examined in detail and the themes related to the situation were described" (Buyukozturk et al., 2014: 21). In the research, During the interviews and meetings with the teachers, the opinions of the teachers regarding the vocational practices were recorded and analyzed, and the case study method was used in the research so that it could be possible to describe the subject in depth, grounded on the interviews and the analyzes.

2.2 Study Group

The study group of the research consists of a total of 30 vocational course teachers, 21 male and 9 female, from different branches working in state-affiliated vocational high schools in the central districts of Hatay province in the 2021-2022 academic year and they participated in the research on a voluntary basis. In order to answer the research problems and propose solutions, the study group was chosen from the teachers who gave vocational

courses. Based on the fact that the number of teachers participating in the research was small, it was possible to conduct an in-depth study of the opinions of the participants. In the research, the participants were determined by using the purposive sampling method (Creswell, 2009). In this context, it was tried to provide field diversity in the vocational course teachers interviewed. In the interviews, in order to get the sincere thoughts of the teachers, it was told to the teachers that the answers to the prepared questions would be kept confidential within the framework of ethical principles and that they would not be used anywhere other than research. The following table shows the demographic information about the study group consisting of vocational teachers.

Table 1: Demographic characteristics of vocational course teachers

Demographic characteristics		F	%
Gender	Female	9	30.00
	Male	21	70.00
Age range	20-25	3	10.00
	26-30	2	6.67
	31-35	4	13.33
	36-40	10	33.33
	41-45	6	20.00
	46 and over	5	16.67
Graduation	Bachelors degree	24	80.00
	Master's Degree	6	20.00
Branch	Biomedical Device Technologies	5	16.67
	Child Development	3	10.00
	Electric Electronic Technology	8	26.67
	Construction Technologies	4	13.33
	Accounting	2	6.67
	Plumbing Technology and Climate	4	13.33
	Food and Beverage Services	4	13.33
Professional experience	1-5 years	12	40.00
	6-10 years	4	13.33
	11-15 years	1	3.33
	16 years or more	13	43.33
Total		30	100.00

When Table 1 is examined, it has been determined that 9 of the 30 vocational course teachers participating in the research are female and 21 are male. There are 3 participants between the ages of 20-25, 2 participants between the ages of 26-30, 4 participants between the ages of 31-35, 10 participants between the ages of 36-40, 6 participants between the ages of 41-45 and 5 participants in the age group 46 and over. It has been determined that 24 of the teachers have bachelors degree and 6 of them have master's degrees. It has been determined that 5 vocational course teachers from the Biomedical Device Technologies branch, 3 from the Child Development branch, 8 from the Electrical and Electronics Technology branch, 4 from the Construction Technologies branch, 2 from the Accounting Field, 4 from the Plumbing Technology and Climate branch, and 4 from the Food and Beverage Services branch participated in the research. It was determined that 12 teachers who participated in the research had work experience between 1-5 years, 4 teachers between 6-10 years, 1 teacher between 11-15 years, and 13 teachers 16 years or more.

2.3 Data Collection Tool

For this research, first of all, a literature study was conducted on vocational education and the problems encountered in vocational education. As a data collection tool, a semi-structured interview form developed by Gur-Erdogan, Demirtas & Ozalan (2020) about vocational practices was used in the research. In order to use the semi-structured interview form in the research, permission was obtained from the researchers via email. For data

collection in the research, the days and exact times of the interviews were determined by meeting with the school administration and teachers. An average of 45 minutes was interviewed with each teacher to collect the research data. In this way, it took approximately 4 weeks to collect the research data.

2.4 Data Analysis

The data obtained as a result of the participant personal information questionnaire, participant interview form, and interviews were arranged in tables and analyzed using descriptive analysis method. In descriptive analysis, the data is organized according to predetermined themes with research questions or presented within the framework of the questions or dimensions used in the interview (Yildirim & Simsek, 2013). In addition, while analyzing the data in the research, the questions in the semi-structured interview form were also used to determine the main themes. The data obtained as a result of the interviews conducted in research can be organized according to the themes under various headings determined within the framework of the research questions and presented around the questions asked in the research (Yildirim & Simsek, 2013).

First of all, teachers filled the forms and the recorded interviews were transcribed from the audio recording and all the data were transferred to the computer in the data analysis process. All the data obtained from the interviews were organized by classification and subjected to content analysis. In order to obtain accurate and reliable findings in the code generation process, the codes determined by the researchers were used in the analyzes in line with the common opinion, by performing coding with 3 associate professor who worked in the field of curriculum development in education and had done coding many times before. The generated codes were tabulated and making the codes understandable was another vital point. the teachers who would participate in the research signed a volunteer agreement document within the framework of ethical rules. The names of the teachers participating in the research were kept confidential throughout the research and the teachers were coded as H1., H2., H3., H4., ...H30.

3. Findings

In this part of the research, the findings, analyzes and analysis of the research is included.

Table 2: Vocational course teachers' opinions about the lack of vocational competence of students

The problem content	Explanations	N	%
Vocational competence of the students	Sufficient (H4,H6,H10,H11,H17,H19,H24,H27,H28,H29)	10	33.33
	Partially sufficient (H1,H2,H3,H5,H7,H8,H9,H12,H13,H14,H15, H16,H18,H20,H22,H25,H26,H30)	18	60.00
	Insufficient (H21,H23)	2	6.67
Reasons why students do not have vocational competence	Inconsistency of theoretical education with practical training (H7, H8,H10,H11,H12,H13,H14,H15,H20,H21,H22,H24,H26)	13	43.33
	The student's physical inadequacy (H1,H2,H3,H5,H9,H25)	6	20.00
	Lack of practical and theoretical knowledge (H2,H12,H18, H30)	4	13.33
	Behavioral problems (H2,H16,H23,H30)	4	13.33

When Table 2 is examined, 18 of the vocational teachers stated that the students graduated with partial vocational knowledge when they finished their vocational education, while 10 teachers stated that the students graduated with vocational skills. On the other hand, 2 of the teachers think that the students graduated without being aware of their vocational skills. Considering the reasons for students' graduation without vocational qualifications, teachers stated that the inconsistency of theoretical education and the training given in practice (13 participant), the student's physical inadequacy (6 participant), lack of practical and theoretical knowledge (4 participant), behavioral problems (4 participant).

Some of the teacher's statements expressing their opinions on this subject;

“Although some of the students do not have vocational qualifications, the changes made in the regulations for passing a grade level in recent years have negatively affected the learning of the students, allowing them to pass to the next grade despite their lack of knowledge.” (H15).

“Their inability to adopt their profession, lack of knowledge, lack of any concern about the future affect their ability to have vocational competence.” (H28).

“The readiness of the students is one of the main reasons why students cannot gain vocational competence. The attitude of students who have a low level of basic competence and interest in vocational education towards the course negatively affects them.” (H23).

“When students do not support the vocational education they receive at school with repetitions when they go to workplaces, they forget. These forgotten things cause students to have difficulty in following vocational education.” (H13).

Table 3: Opinions of vocational course teachers on the work discipline and adaptation status of students who receive internship training at workplaces

The problem content	Explanations	N	%
Adaptation of intern students to work discipline	They have difficulty in following the rules (H3,H9,H10,H11,H12,H14,H15, H18,H20,H22,H30)	11	36.67
	They have some difficulty in following the rules (H1,H2,H4,H5,H6, H7,H8, H16,H19,H20,H21,H23,H24,H25,H26,H27,H28,H29)	18	60.00
	They don't have any difficulty in following the rules (H13,H17)	2	6.67
Reasons why students find it difficult to adapt to work discipline	Students' not being accustomed to the regular work process (H1,H2,H4,H5, H7,H11,H12,H15,H18,H20,H26,H27,H29,H30)	14	46.67
	Reluctance (H2,H3,H5,H7,H14,H20,H21,H23,H25)	9	30.00
	Inability to understand work discipline (H16,H18,H24,H30)	4	13.33
	Unwillingness to take responsibility (H6,H7,H8,H9,H10,H12,H19,H20,H21, H22,H28)	11	36.67
	Not being taken seriously by experienced or knowledgeable employees (H3, H21)	2	6.67

When Table 3 is examined, 11 of the vocational teachers stated that the students had difficulty in getting used to the order in the workplace, 18 teachers stated that the students had some difficulties in getting used to it, and 2 teachers stated that the students did not have any difficulty in getting used to work discipline. When the reasons why students have difficulty in getting used to the workplace discipline are examined, vocational course teachers think that students are not used to working at this pace ($N=14$), they think that students have a weak interest in acquiring a profession ($N=9$), they think that students are not satisfied with the position they work ($N=4$), they think that students have problems due to their personality traits ($N=11$) and they think that experienced or knowledgeable employees are indifferent to students ($N=2$).

Some of the teacher's statements expressing their opinions on this subject;

“Spending too much time on social media and taking the events there as an example causes them to have difficulty in adapting to the work discipline. In addition, we can say that they have difficulty in adapting because they are out of the discipline they were used to.” (H3)

“They have difficulties because they cannot grasp whether they have vocational qualifications or not, and they do not exactly understand the need to work in a disciplined system.” (H14)

“The reason why work discipline cannot be provided in the educational environment may be due to many reasons. The first of these may be that the workshop rules are not clearly stated and the teacher does not have professional competence.” (H6)

“In recent years, education has been insufficient because students have taken distance education courses due to the pandemic. Therefore, students have difficulty in maintaining work discipline. (H7).

Table 4: Vocational course teachers' thoughts on the problems related to vocational practice training and the causes of the problems

The problem content	Explanations	N	%
Problems of vocational teachers related to internship training arising from students	I have problems with skills training (H2,H3,H4,H5,H12,H16,H21,H22,H25,H26,H28,H29,H30)	13	43.33
	I don't have problems with skill training (H1,H7,H8,H10,H11,H13,H14,H15,H17,H18,H19,H20,H23,H24)	14	46.67
The reasons for the problems that teachers encounter in internship training related to students	Workplace or employer-related problems (H10,H11,H12,H14,H29,H30)	6	20.00
	Problems stemming from individual differences (H5,H6,H7,H8,H9,H10,H16,H18,H19,H20,H21,H22,H25,H28)	14	46.67
	Absenteeism or problems with classes (H2,H9,H10,H21,H26,H30)	6	20.00
	Motivation or adaptation problems (H2,H3,H4,H5,H12,H15,H27)	7	23.33

When Table 4 is examined, 13 teachers who participated in the research stated that their students had problems with skill training ($N=13$), while 14 teachers stated that they did not encounter any problems ($N=14$). According to the teachers, the reasons for the problems experienced by the students in the internship training are the problems caused by the workplace or the employer ($N=6$), the problems arising from individual differences ($N=14$), the problems caused by the students' absenteeism ($N=6$) and the problems caused by the students having difficulties in adapting ($N=7$). Some of the opinions of vocational course teachers are given below with one-on-one citations.

Some of the teacher's statements expressing an opinion on this issue;

"The reasons why students encounter problems in vocational practice are that they have difficulty in adapting to disciplined work and do not take the warnings of the qualified instructor seriously." (H9).

"The reason for the problems is that they do not think that they are required to participate, that they do not understand the importance of internship, that they do not understand the purpose of the internship, that the workplaces cannot provide adequate confidence to the students." (H21).

"The reasons for the problems are the inadequacy of the workplaces in the education of the students, the indifference of the students towards their own fields, the fact that the students behave as if the school is over because the internships are in the last year." (H29).

"I think that the main source of the problems is that students consider the internship as a burden and obligation for them. However, if they accept that the internship period is an opportunity for them, many problems will disappear." (H30).

Table 5: Vocational course teachers' thoughts on the achievement of the determined goal of vocational practice training

The problem content	Explanations	N	%
Achieving the goal of internship training	It reaches its goal, purpose (H9,H17,H19,H24,H27,H29).	6	20.00
	It partially achieves its goal, purpose (H1,H2,H3,H4,H5,H6,H7,H8,H10,H11,H12,H13,H14,H15,H16,H18,H20,H21,H22,H23,H25,H26,H28,H30).	24	80.00
	It does not reach its goal, purpose.	0	0.00

When Table 5 is examined, ($N=6$) teachers who participated in the research think that the internship training has achieved its goal, ($N=24$) the teacher think that internship training has partially achieved its goal, and ($N=0$) the teacher thinks that the internship training has not reached its goal.

Some of the expressions of teachers expressing their opinions on this subject;

“Students who go to the workplace for learning purposes do not have any difficulties in terms of learning. However, unfortunately, positive results cannot be obtained for students who do not like the profession or behave reluctantly.” (H2).

“The main reason why the internship does not comply with its purpose is that it is compulsory to do the internship and the students do the internship only for the purpose of completing it.” (H21).

“My experience as a coordinator shows me that when students who care about internship education and conscious workplaces come together, I think that efficiency will increase and students will gain more experience.” (H21).

“Internship training is important for the student to see the workplace environment, to adapt to workplace rules, to see and experience the negativities that may occur in business life.” (H17).

Table 6: Vocational course teachers' opinions on the improvement of vocational training

The problem content	Explanations	N	%
Recommendations for improving vocational education	Curriculum should be rearranged (H4,H7,H10,H11,H12,H20,H25).	7	23.33
	Practical course time should be increased (H19,H24).	3	10.00
	There should be cooperation between vocational high schools, state institutions and workplaces (H2,H3,H4,H5,H6,H7,H9,H10,H11,H12,H13,H14,H15,H18,H19,H20,H21,H22,H26,H27,H28,H29,H30).	23	76.67
	The scope of internship training should be increased (H2,H3,H6,H7,H11,H18,H19,H20,H21,H27,H29).	11	36.67
	Opportunities of vocational high schools should be increased (H1,H2,H4, H5,H6,H7,H12,H13,H14,H19,H20,H29,H30).	13	43.33
	Students should be admitted to vocational education institutions with an aptitude test (H2,H3,H5,H6,H7,H8,H9,H10,H11,H12,H14,H16,H17, H19,H20,H2,H22,H23).	18	60.00

When Table 6 is examined, the suggestions of the vocational course teachers who participated in the research for the improvement of vocational education are as follows; curricula should be rearranged ($N=7$), practical course time should be increased ($N=3$), there should be cooperation between vocational high schools, state institutions and workplaces ($N=23$), the scope of internship training should be increased ($N=11$), the opportunities of vocational high schools should be increased ($N=13$) and students must be admitted to vocational education institutions with an aptitude test ($N=18$).

Some of the statements of teachers expressing their opinions on this subject;

“Practical training should be given more time, the curriculum should be simplified, and the work environment and economic conditions of teachers should be improved.” (H13).

“My suggestions are to have sufficient equipment at the internship places, to cover the damages that students will cause to the workplace during the education, and to instill self-confidence in the students.” (H24).

“I believe that vocational education schools should be closer to the market and production points (organized industrial zones, government institutions, etc.) and that cooperation with different facilities is absolutely necessary. In this way, students will complete their development by receiving more realistic and more up-to-date education.” (H19).

“It will be healthier for the students and the school if the internship training is given at different times from the school education instead of being given simultaneously.” (H28).

4. Conclusion and Recommendations

In this section, the findings obtained from the answers given by the teachers participating in the research to the data collection tool were evaluated and the results and recommendations regarding the students' achievements in obtaining a profession, internship training and the problems encountered during vocational education are given.

4.1 Conclusion

In the research, based on the answers given by the vocational course teachers, it was concluded that the students did not have enough professional competence when they graduated. From the interviews with the teachers, it was determined that the reasons for this situation stemmed from problems such as lack of knowledge, different applied trainings, inability to follow technological developments, and not repeating the skills learned at school in workplaces. In a study by Nayir, (2006), it was found out that the theoretical knowledge that students learn in schools is not sufficient for them to practice during skill training in workplace.

In the research, it was concluded that vocational teachers could not implement the curriculum as they wished, that some courses in the curriculum had few weekly course hours and that their schools had weak network with other workplaces. In a study by Dahil, Karabulut and Mutlu, (2015), it was deduced that the course hours of vocational practices should be increased and courses related to technological developments should be added to the curriculum. In a study conducted by Aslanturk (2014), it was concluded that it is very important to ensure the integrity of the curriculum in vocational schools, to increase the number of practical courses, and to strengthen the links between vocational education and business areas in the sector.

In the research, it was concluded that the students had difficulty in getting used to the vocational education they received and the discipline in the work environment. From the interviews with the teachers, it was determined that the reasons for this situation were that the students could not get used to the workload and the speed of work and their interest in their profession was weak. In a study conducted by Zengin, (2014), it was concluded that students could not get used to the workload and speed of work, and this was due to their weak interest in their profession. A study conducted by Jones (2018) also concluded that vocational education is very important for the development of high-level skills and the ability of individuals to adapt to conditions in the workplace, so much more research should be done on this subject.

In the study, it was also determined that teachers had some problems related to skill training caused by students. From interviews with teachers, it was determined that the reasons for this situation are mostly due to the personality of the students, their behavior, as well as the work and employer. In a study by Ozer (2019), it was found out that the reason for the lack of cooperation between schools and the vocational sector is that the students studying at vocational high schools are less successful than the students in other schools and they are less interested in vocational training and courses. Problems with students in schools should not be neglected. Because neglected problems can cause bigger problems and chaos over time (Yavas, 2022).

In the research, one of the student-related problems is that the students do not take the warnings of the qualified instructors seriously, do not comply with the work discipline, and they think that going to the internship is just compulsory. Another problem is that workplaces lack education and do not provide adequate support and education to students. In a study conducted by Akkus-Aydemir, (2015), the conclusion was that the reason why students do not take vocational practices seriously is due to reasons such as not telling students enough about the machinery and equipment at workplace and not having enough practice, as well as not working in the fields or jobs students are studying.

In the research, it has been concluded that according to some teachers, vocational education has been successful in educating students as qualified, and according to some teachers, professional practices in vocational education partially reach their goal. Vocational education is very important especially for students who graduate from vocational schools. Of course, theoretical courses should be included in vocational schools. However, it should not be forgotten that the main purpose of vocational schools is to train qualified personnel. This can only be achieved through vocational practices that achieve their goals.

4.2 Recommendations

Taking into account the changing world, developing technology and the opinions of vocational course teachers, vocational lessons and vocational practices should be reviewed and the necessary arrangements should be made as soon as possible.

Relevant institutions and organizations should find solutions to all the problems in the curriculum, especially the application days and hours related to vocational practices, and to increase or strengthen the cooperation between vocational schools and other workplaces by interviewing vocational teachers.

Both vocational and theoretical courses to be given to the students in vocational schools should be of a quality that will enable the student to acquire all the knowledge and skills that may be required in the profession. Thanks to the core trainings that will be given to the student through vocational education, the student should be able to easily find a place for himself/herself in the future career, and thanks to the trainings s/he have received, he should be able to constantly update himself on new technology with ease. Hence, vocational education in schools and theoretical education should be combined and supported by training in workplaces.

Both professional teachers and other teachers who feel inadequate or think that they have deficiencies should be provided with in-service trainings by the relevant institutions and the deficiencies of teachers should be made up. Since vocational schools provide education all day, both physical and financial opportunities of teachers, students and schools should be improved.

Vocational schools should be in contact with other workplaces, and students should be trained on the type of qualified people demanded by the markets or workplaces and the jobs requested.

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